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RESEARCH OF REVERSE POLARITY ARC IN PLASMA CUTTING PROCESSES

Summary.

The work is devoted to experimental studies of the processes occurring in the electric arc of cutting plasma torches of reverse polarity with an anode electrode. It has been established that in order to increase the service life of such plasma torches, the arc current should be limited, and an increase in power should be obtained by lengthening it. As the arc lengthens and resistance increases, its sensitivity to fluctuations in the blowing air flow increases, which leads to a decrease in stability and spontaneous extinction of the arc. Studies have shown an increase in the service life of the anode electrode compared to a traditional cathode electrode by up to 5 times at a cutting current of 200 A. Additional application of high-frequency voltage to the arc initiates the SKIN effect in the peripheral zone of the arc discharge. At the same time, contraction of the arc improves and the stability of its combustion increases; the conduction zone and maximum temperature shift to the periphery of the arc column. This may help reduce erosion of cold electrodes. The power source must ensure stable burning of the electric arc, maintaining and regulating the electrical modes of the plasma torch within specified limits, and transition from one point in the phase space to another along a given trajectory. An electric arc, as an element of the electrical circuit of the power supply system, is characterized by significantly inhomogeneous conditions along the length of the arc column.

Keywords: *air plasma cutting, reverse polarity, plasma torch, anode electrode, current and voltage oscillograms, erosion, resource.*

Increasing requirements for modern structural materials causes corresponding increased requirements for metallurgical units, which must ensure their processing, including thermal processing [1]. Due to obvious advantages, as well as the relative ease of technical use, low-temperature plasma is widely introduced into mechanical engineering and metalworking: the processes of cutting, spraying, melting, welding, spheroidization [2]. To solve these problems, there are numerous technological and design schemes of arc plasma torches [3]. In the case of air plasma cutting, two process schemes have gained the greatest popularity - direct and reverse polarity. The case of plasma cutting with direct polarity is quite popular and well studied [4]. Therefore, in this work we will talk about studying the features of air plasma cutting with reverse polarity (electrode - anode, part - cathode).

The relevance of the work is related to the need to increase the efficiency and controllability of heating materials in plasma jets of reverse polarity, the productivity of the cutting process with such jets and

expanding the possibilities of using air plasma cutting technologies with reverse polarity.

The purpose of the work is to conduct experimental studies of the processes occurring in the electric arc of cutting plasma torches of reverse polarity, during their technological use for cutting metal materials.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved: creation of an experimental stand to study the features of a reverse polarity arc; carrying out the necessary research; analysis of the information obtained and comparison of the results with similar results for an arc of direct polarity.

The experiments were carried out on a laboratory setup (Fig. 1), consisting of a power source, a cutting plasma torch (Fig. 1, a), a sectioned calorimeter (Fig. 1, b), a device for measuring the current flowing through each section, a device for measuring the temperature of the cooling water at the inlet and outlet of each section of the calorimeter, measuring instruments and control devices for the operation of the plasmatron.

Fig. 1. Scheme (a) of plasma cutting with reverse polarity and sketch (b) of a laboratory setup for studying the cutting arc: 1 – sections; 2 – gap; 3 – water inlet and outlet fittings.

To study the distribution of current and heat flow along the length of the cutting cavity, a sectional calorimeter was developed (Fig. 1b), consisting of 10 flat cylindrical sections 1 with a diameter of 100 mm and a thickness of 9.8 mm. The sections were separated from each other by fiberglass gaskets 0.2 mm thick, which ensured their reliable electrical and thermal insulation from the axis to the outer cylindrical surface of each section, a slot 2 wide 8 mm was cut. When all sections are assembled, these slots form a model of the cutting cavity. Each section is cooled with running water. Water is supplied through a hose to fitting 3, and then flows through channels drilled in the copper section to the outlet fitting and is diverted from the section through the hose. For ease of connecting the hoses, the fittings are welded to the sections offset relative to each other.

One of the poles of the power source was connected to the internal electrode, and the second through the ballast resistance R_b and the power contacts of the contactor of the standby circuit for connection to the nozzle electrode of the plasmatron, as well as through the measuring resistances R_u – to each of the sections of the calorimeter. Identical sections of stainless steel tubes were used as measuring resistances. Cooling water was supplied to each section through these tubes. Cooling the tubes ensured the stability of their resistance. The amount of current passing through a particular section was determined by the magnitude of the voltage drop across the measuring resistance R_u . To measure this voltage, a millivoltmeter

of accuracy class 0.5 was used. In order to reduce the error, the measurement was carried out by the same device, alternately connected using a switch to the measuring resistances of the sections.

The magnitudes of heat flows along the length of the cut were determined from the measured temperatures of water at the inlet and outlet of the sections and its flow through the sections. Transistor temperature sensors were used to determine the temperature of the cooling water. The total arc current and operating voltage were measured, respectively, with an ammeter and a voltmeter of accuracy class 0.5.

It should be noted that the proposed model of the cutting cavity differs to some extent from the real one, primarily in the absence of molten metal in it, as well as the lower temperatures of its front and side walls. Under these conditions, it can be expected that the establishment of the average arc length, shunting processes and arc field strength will also differ somewhat from the real ones.

To check the acceptability of the proposed model, a series of experiments was carried out in which the current-voltage characteristics of an arc burning in a sectional calorimeter and in real metal cutting conditions were compared. Experiments have shown that in the studied ranges of change in current, plasma air flow rate and nozzle hole diameter, the current-voltage characteristics differ by 5-15%. This allows us to consider the arc burning conditions and the nature of its behavior in a sectional calorimeter to be close to real conditions.

Depending on the ratio of the geometric dimensions of the arc channel and the gas supply unit in a plasmatron with hollow copper electrodes, three different operating modes are possible. *The first mode* is characterized by stable operation with small-scale

pulsations of current and voltage (Fig. 2). In this case, the arc occupies a stable spatial position in the channel over time.

Fig. 2. Typical oscillograms of current and voltage of a plasma torch with hollow copper electrodes.

In *the second mode*, due to the gas-dynamic instability of the vortex flow in the blind electrode, the average arc length can change. The arc in the plasmatron channel seems to be trying to find a stable position and does not find it. Along with a change in

the average length, the arc moves from one current-voltage characteristic to another (Fig. 3). At such moments, spontaneous extinction of the arc is possible (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Drift of arc parameters.

Fig. 4. Spontaneous arc extinction.

The “source-arc” system is fundamentally stable if, as a result of processing small disturbances, it reaches a steady state of equilibrium, characterized by equality of supplied and consumed energy and small deviations of current and voltage from the initial state. It is known that the “source-arc” system is stable under small disturbances if the difference in the differential resistances of the arc and the source at the point of intersection of their characteristics is positive - “stable in small.”

However, as follows from Fig. 4, the condition of fundamental stability is not enough. During operation of the plasma torch, significant disturbances are fluctuations in the average arc length. The more you can lengthen the arc, the more stable the process. The breaking length of the arc was determined experimentally. The parameters of the breaking arc length for the power supply system used in the experiments for an open free-burning arc are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Arc breaking length parameters.

No	U idling (M)	U break (V)	I break (A)	L break (mm)
1	640	195	200	240
2	640	200	300	300

The average length of the arc burning in a plasma torch with a hollow copper anode electrode with a power of 200 kW is 140 mm, so that in the absence of drift and fluctuations there is a sufficient reserve of arc elasticity.

In the *third mode*, the arc burning mode with large-scale pulsations is realized (Fig. 5), when the shunt zone occupies several times larger area than in the case of small-scale pulsations. In this case, large-

scale pulsations are superimposed on small-scale pulsations. In this case, the current load is distributed evenly over a larger area, which helps to increase the service life of the plasma torch as a whole. A notable property of this mode of operation of a plasma torch with a hollow copper anode electrode is the excitation of high-frequency harmonic damped oscillations at the moment of breakdown.

Fig. 5. Oscillograms of current and voltage of a plasmatron with a hollow copper anode electrode in large-scale shunt mode.

It is clearly seen here that a plasma torch with a hollow copper anode electrode operates under conditions of constant transient processes and the arc in it is less stable. Under certain conditions, the “electric arc – source” system forms a self-oscillating system [5] or enters into electrodynamic resonance. In this case, the frequency of the oscillatory circuit of the LC source coincides with the natural pulsation frequency of the near-electrode sections of the arc, caused by shunting. For this case, this frequency was ~ 700 Hz, the displacement speed of the cathode arc spot was ~ 33 m/sec.

A more detailed study of the shunting processes in such a plasmatron revealed the phenomenon of generation of damped harmonic oscillations with a frequency of the order of 1 MHz (Fig. 6).

The transition to the arc burning mode with the generation of high-frequency oscillations (Fig. 6) is accompanied by an elongation of the initial section of the plasma jet by 1.5-2 times and an increase in the radiation intensity. This indicates a prolongation of relaxation processes in the plasma and is most likely associated with the occurrence of vibrational nonequilibrium due to the generation of powerful acoustic ultrasonic vibrations.

Fig. 6. Generation of damped harmonic oscillations.

In addition, the additional application of high-frequency voltage to the arc initiates the SKIN effect in the peripheral zone of the arc discharge. At the same time, the contraction of the arc improves and the stability of its combustion increases. The conduction zone, respectively the current lines, and the maximum temperature due to the SKIN effect is shifted from the arc column to its periphery. An important consequence of this effect is a shift in the pulsating magnetic field in the near-cathode and near-anode zones of the discharge with a concomitant shift in the electron flow in the Ampereian direction. According to the authors, such a complex of phenomena should influence the evolution of the substructure of the cathode and anode arc spots and contribute to the inclusion of new active spot surfaces. It is expected that at a given current there will be a redistribution of the current density over a larger emission surface. In our opinion, this process contains the prerequisites for a significant reduction in the erosion of cold electrodes.

In high-power plasma torches, due to stretching the electric arc and intensifying its cooling with the transition to steam (as a plasma-forming gas), the voltage on the arc increases, and the arc time constant decreases, so the requirements for the dynamic characteristics of the source increase. These characteristics are determined by the parameters of the control circuit, power regulator and filter. The requirements for them apply to a wide range of frequencies: the lowest (inertia of processes in a plasma installation) is determined by gas-dynamic, chemical and thermal phenomena in the plasma jet and is a fraction of a Hz, the upper – by the processes of ionization and deionization, is several MHz. The operation of the plasma torch in non-stationary and transient modes is determined by the operating algorithm of the power supply, and the plasma arc is considered as an inertia-free element with a static nonlinear characteristic.

Increasing the service life of copper electrodes requires a detailed study of the issues of current transfer

and heat exchange in the near-electrode areas of the arc in relation to this plasmatron design. The rate of erosion of copper electrodes (cathode and anode) is determined by many factors and especially by the magnitude of the arc current. Moreover, the erosion characteristics of the anode and cathode can either completely coincide or show a significant discrepancy - depending on the dynamics of near-electrode processes. In the air environment there is a critical regime - a current value, above which the erosion of the material increases sharply. The reason for the appearance of a critical

mode is the loss of rotational stability of the gas flow in the electrode cavity. One of the main issues is to ensure that the level of specific erosion of electrodes remains unchanged during long-term operation in the range of subcritical currents. The erosion of a copper hollow cathode in an air atmosphere is about $\approx 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ kg/C, the average level of erosion of the electrode-anode is lower and is $\approx 4 \cdot 10^{-11}$ kg/C. After 50 hours of operation, cracking along the grain boundaries appears in the surface layer of the electrode material (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Cracking of a copper cathode in the surface layer ($\times 200$).

The cathode cracks to a greater depth - approximately twice as deep as the anode. The erosion surface at the anode is less oxidized than the cathode surface. Thus, the erosion of copper electrodes is mainly determined by the heat flux density and the speed of movement of the near-electrode sections of the arc. By ensuring good stability of the electrodes, today we can talk about a guaranteed service life of the cathode when working in air - 200 hours, the anode - 1000 hours at a current of 200 A and a material operating depth of $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. When water vapor is added to the plasma-forming air, erosion of the cathode and anode is noticeably reduced due to the reducing atmosphere. The authors have not carried out precise life tests, however, experience in the industrial operation of gas-air plasma torches indicates a multiple reduction in erosion [6].

Conclusions.

1. It has been established that in order to increase the service life of the plasma torch, the arc current should be limited, and an increase in power should be obtained due to an increase in its resistance and a drop in voltage across it, i.e. arc lengthening. As the arc lengthens and its resistance increases, its sensitivity to fluctuations in the air flow increases, which leads to a decrease in stability and spontaneous extinction of the arc. This problem is common to all types of plasma torches. As the arc lengthens and the blowing intensifies, the requirements for the dynamic properties of the power source increase.

2. It has been established that additional application of high-frequency voltage to the arc initiates the SKIN effect in the peripheral zone of the arc discharge. At the same time, contraction of the arc improves and the stability of its combustion increases; the conduction zone and maximum temperature shift to

the periphery of the arc column. This complex of phenomena can contribute to the inclusion of new active surfaces of the cathode and anode spots. It is expected that at a given current there will be a redistribution of the current density over a larger emission surface, which will help reduce the erosion of cold electrodes.

3. By ensuring stable operation of the electrodes of traditional plasma torches (cathodes) and reverse polarity plasma torches (anodes) when operating in air, a guaranteed service life of the cathode is achieved up to 200 hours, the anode - up to 1000 hours at a current of 200 A and a material actuation depth of $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. By adding water vapor to the plasma-forming air, erosion of the cathode and anode is noticeably reduced due to the reducing atmosphere.

4. The power source must ensure stable burning of the electric arc, maintaining and regulating the electrical modes of the plasma torch within specified limits, and transition from one point in the phase space to another along a given trajectory. An electric arc, as an element of the electrical circuit of the power supply system, is characterized by significantly inhomogeneous conditions along the length of the arc column. Its combustion is accompanied by a variety of complex interconnected physical phenomena, electromagnetic, thermal, gas-dynamic, chemical, etc. An electric arc, as an element of an electrical circuit, is characterized primarily by the relationship between current and voltage, i.e. static and dynamic characteristics.

Gratitude

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